

Dear Imamsaheb S.J.,

Head AICRP Tuber crops,
RHREC, Dharwad,-
431402.

Manuscript ID: IJARVM/aug25200764

Dear Author(S):

This is to inform you that your paper entitled “*Performance of Biofortified Sweet Potato Genotypes for Growth and Tuber Productivity Under the Northern Transition Zone of Karnataka*” has been accepted by the editorial board based on the reviewers’ reports and editorial considerations. Hope your paper will satisfy the interest of the readers.

Category: **Agriculture (All)**

Status: **Accepted**

Thanks again for your kind interest in Special issue/Regular Issue of *International Journal of Applied Research in Veterinary Medicine (Dec-2025)*

Please feel free to contact if you require additional information. **Please share the APC Receipt today.**

Sincerely,

Editor

Executive Editor

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Enclosures: (i) Reviewers’ Reports – Page 2

(ii) Terms & Conditions – Page3

International Journal of Applied Research in Veterinary Medicine

Editor-in-Chief:

Reviewer – 1 and 2

Evaluation Criteria	Yes	No
The paper makes original influence	√	
The papers is well Formatted	√	
Author Guidelines has been followed properly in preparing the manuscript	√	
The paper is based on rigorous approach	√	
Literature review is adequate	√	
Analysis and findings support objectives of the paper	√	

Decision regarding the paper

- (*) Accept the paper in its current format
- () Accept the paper with the minor changes
- () Resubmit with the major changes
- () Decline the submission

Comments and Suggestions

This is an excellent investigation report, and I approve of its publication. The paper is well organized. In my opinion, the paper is publishable with no significant revision.

E-mail & Contact Number of Corresponding Author

The corresponding author must mention her/his email id & contact number in the paper.

Terms & Conditions

Schedule of Publication

The paper is scheduled to be published in IJARVM. You will get the print copy within four weeks after online publication **if ordered**. (Charges for hard copy applicable)

Invoice

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